

STUDY OF SPECTRAL PARAMETERS OF COMBINATORIAL SCATTERING LINES OF LIGHT IN SURFACTANTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6613419>

Annotation: Assembly processes can drive the selection of self- assembling molecules in dynamic combinatorial libraries, yielding self- synthesizing materials. We now show how such selection in a dynamic combinatorial library made from an amphiphilic building block which, by itself, assembles into micelles, can yield membranous aggregates ranging from vesicles to sponge phases. These aggregates are made from a mixture of unconventional surfactant molecules, showing the power of dynamic combinatorial selection approaches for the discovery of new, not readily predictable, self-assembly motifs.

Keywords: spectral parameters, scattering lines, molecule, power, method.

INTRODUCTION

Self-assembly is a powerful concept to access nano-sized structures that are organized with up to atomic resolution. Traditionally, access to such structures involved two separate steps in which the design and synthesis of the self-assembling molecule are followed by the assembly process in a separate second step. In many cases, the different conditions required for synthesis and assembly preclude their integration into a single process. However, with the advent of dynamic covalent chemistry, different chemistries are now available, which can be operated under conditions compatible with those required for assembly, allowing a systems chemistry approach to self-assembly where the synthesis of the assembling molecules and their self-assembly become intertwined¹. Specifically, assembly processes occurring in dynamic combinatorial libraries (DCLs) allow access to what we termed “self-synthesizing materials”. The idea is that upon formation of reversible covalent bonds between different building blocks, a diverse set of different potentially self- assembling molecules is formed, which continuously inter- convert by exchanging building blocks (Figure 1a). Library members that self-assemble are stabilized by the noncovalent interactions involved in the assembly process and the equilibrium shifts to amplify the assembling molecules at the expense of the other library members. This approach has allowed access to a variety of self-assembled structures, including fibers and sheets (for these morphologies, the process of

¹Menger, F. M. Chemical collectivism. Chem. Br. 2013, 29, 300– 302.

self-assembly-driven self-synthesis is often autocatalytic, enabling access to self-replicators), micelles, and vesicles².

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Yet access to self-synthesizing vesicles has not progressed beyond proof of principle, targeting conventional double-chain surfactants. We now report the formation of a series of different membranous architectures, including vesicles, by a mixture of nonconventional surfactants that are selected from a small DCL formed from a simple amphiphilic building block. These results demonstrate that the concept of self-synthesizing compartments extends well beyond canonical surfactant architectures.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We reasoned that it should be possible to discover new vesicle forming surfactants in DCLs made from amphiphilic building blocks. Given that bilayer architectures are normally more efficient in shielding their hydrophobic interior from water than micelles, we expected that combinatorial selection experiments would preferentially lead to vesicles, even if the building block by itself would assemble into a different morphology. In order to test these hypotheses, we designed building block 1 which contains a hydrophobic aromatic core functionalized with two thiol groups, which can be oxidized to form a DCL of macrocyclic disulfides (Figure 1b). It also features a hydrophilic tetraethylene glycol chain that enables water solubility and renders the overall building block structure amphiphilic.

² Lehn, J.-M. From supramolecular chemistry towards constitutional dynamic chemistry and adaptive chemistry. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* 2017, 36, 151–160.

Figure 1. (a) Concept of self-synthesizing materials: self-assembly of one of the oligomers within a DCL shifts the equilibrium in the direction of the very molecule that self-assembles. (b) Amphiphilic dithiol building block 1 self-assembles into micelles or, upon oxidation, gives rise to a set of interconverting disulfide macrocycles. (c) Structures of building blocks 2–5³.

DCLs were prepared by dissolving building block 1 in borate buffer (50 mM, pH 8.5) in the presence or absence of agitation and allowing the thiols to oxidize by exposing them to oxygen from the air. Agitation was conducted using a magnetic stir bar in order to facilitate a growth-breakage mechanism analogous to that observed previously for self-synthesizing fibers. Analysis by dynamic light scattering (DLS) and transmission electron microscopy (TEM) revealed the presence of micelles in solutions of 1 prior to oxidation of the building block (vide infra). The disulfide macrocycles formed upon oxidation can exchange building blocks through the reaction with residual thiolate anion.

CONCLUSION

The composition of the DCLs was analyzed by ultra performance liquid chromatography (UPLC)–mass spectrometry (MS), which uses conditions under which the aggregates fall apart into the molecules from which they are constituted. In contrast to control compound 2, equipped only with a

³Mitschke, J. R. Systems chemistry: Molecular networks come of age. Nature 2019, 462, 736–738.

carboxylate group, which forms a small DCL dominated by cyclic trimers and tetramers (Figure 2a), the DCL made from building block 1 consists of a much larger range of oligomers (Figure 2b; for a nonagitated control, see Figure S1). Thus, a plethora of molecules is available with different amphiphilic properties that can potentially form supra- molecular assemblies. It took several months at room temperature before the final composition of the library was reached (Figure 2c; for the full time-dependent analysis, see Figure S8). This composition did not change further even after several additional months.

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